

Management Competency of School Heads: Basis for Effective and Improved School Leadership

Jerick S. Aguilar

Graduate Studies and Applied Research, Laguna State Polytechnic University, Philippines

ABSTRACT: The increasing responsibilities of the school heads as school leaders led to the analysis of management competency of school heads perceived by the public elementary grade teachers of Lucena West District. The study revealed that the school heads' management competencies are evident in terms of instructional skills, personnel skills, and financial skills as perceived by the schoolteachers. Findings showed that there is no significant difference in the perceived level of management competency between male and female teacher-respondents in personnel skills, except in instructional skills in terms of visibility and career motivation. There is also a significant difference between the perception of male and female respondents about the management competency in financial skills in terms of audit or financial control. There is no significant difference in the perceived level of management competency between male and female school heads, except in instructional skills in terms of instructional time as perceived by the school heads. There is a positive and significant relationship between the independent variable, perceived management competency and the dependent variable, school leadership in all the dimensions based on the perception of the teacher-respondents. Therefore, the school heads in the division may utilize the findings of the study in developing an employee enhancement program based on all the indicators considered. In addition, due to the limited number of school heads needed for accurate analyses of the relationships of the factors under management competency and school leadership, more samples for the school heads as respondents should be considered in future research.

KEYWORDS: Financial Skills, Instructional Skills, Management Competency, Personnel Skills, School Leadership

INTRODUCTION

Educational management as they're foreseen to elevate quality education and to promote effective and improved school leadership towards a better school. Effective and improved level of management competency gives gamut of desired outcome and radiates positive effect in the whole academe in general. [1]. In running the schools smoothly, the school head must plan, coordinate, and supervise the affairs [2]. The quality of teaching service and the quality of the administrative service provided in the school are equally important. Moreover, they emphasized that it involves the control of human and material resources for the achievement of the school goals and objectives [3]. Management is the arrangement of available human and material resources for the achievement of desired goals and objectives. Competency is however looked at in terms of skills. It is the state of being functionally adequate in the performance of one's duty [4].

The functions of school heads as outlined include management of instructional programs, staff personnel and students' personnel managements, financial and physical resource management, and community relationship management [5]. Furthermore, the vital support for an effective personnel management are communication skills, leadership skills and decision-making skills [6].

Aside from being a Financial Advisor, an English Department Coordinator, a team leader of School-Based Management in school, and a School Paper Adviser/Campus Journalist, the researcher is a public elementary grade teacher who is aware to the increasing duties and responsibilities of school heads and exposed to their critical role as he functioned as the grade leader in his school during the pandemic. Being courageous enough and fortunate to be situated in the wings toward leading a mega school, the researcher realized that managing the entire school is not easy. There are numerous responsibilities that he experienced that time. Throughout the journey, he witnessed how the school leader handled the heaviest responsibility to give and to provide the best in improving teaching and learning processes. In view of this, there are several realizations: firstly, school heads have the very crucial position and always had the higher responsibility and expectation to each school in terms of providing quality education. Secondly, he deemed that school heads must be open for changing their roles to support the school improvement to meet the requirement for educational restructuring.

The school heads are required to play the multiple roles such as being instructional leader, accounting officer, and public relation officer, among others. Moreover, a picture of school head as an administrative head, a manager, a community public relation man,

Management Competency of School Heads: Basis for Effective and Improved School Leadership

a supervisor, an instructional leader, a curriculum innovator, and a catalyst towards planned revolution. With these in mind, it seemed to be necessary to explore the management competency of school heads [7].

The current research explored ample number of factors/variables to study management competency and leadership skills of the school heads. These factors are...

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Aware with the increasing responsibilities of the school heads as school leader, the researcher aims to analyze the management competency of school heads perceived by the public elementary grade teachers of Lucena West District for the school year 2022 – 2023 to create basis for effective and improved school leadership.

Specifically, the study attempted to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of management competency of school heads as perceived by the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 . Instructional skills,
 - 1.2 . Personnel skills, and
 - 1.3 . Financial skills?
2. What is the level of school leadership in terms of:
 - 2.1. Infrastructure,
 - 2.2. Curriculum,
 - 2.3. Academic performance,
 - 2.4. Funding,
 - 2.5. Motivation, and
 - 2.6. Professional growth?
3. Is there a significant difference between the perceived level of management competency of the respondents when grouped according to sex?
4. Is there a significant relationship between management competency and the school leadership of school heads in Lucena West District?
5. What are the possible suggestions and implications for promoting effective and improved school leadership?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher used *correlational research* which is a non-experimental quantitative design applying correlational statistics to measure and describe the degree of association among variables or sets of scores/perceptions with regards to school heads' management competency as perceived by the public elementary school teachers in Lucena West District [8].

Sampling Technique

The schools were **purposively chosen**. In choosing the respondents, the researcher applied the random sampling technique wherein every teacher is welcome to participate. However, it demands that they should be a permanent teacher in the said public schools chosen for the study.

The respondents of the study were the 100 public elementary school teachers who are currently teaching in Lucena West District schools and the 10 school heads.

Research Instrument

Specifically, the researcher's instrument has three (3) major parts that composed the independent variables. Meanwhile, there is an additional one part (the fourth part) which channels that dependent variable.

Part I is a 5-point likert scale which is all about the Instructional Management Skills along with it are the 1.1. School's Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives (VMGO) (5-items), 1.2. Supervision and Evaluation (5-items), 1.3. Curriculum Coordination (5-items), 1.4. Student Progress (5-items), 1.5. Instructional Time (5-items), 1.6. Visibility (5-items), 1.7. Incentives for Teachers (5-items), 1.8. Incentives for Learning (5-items), 1.9. Career Motivations (5-items) and 1.10. Professional Development (5-items).

Furthermore, the Part II has 5-point likert scale and is all about the Personnel Management Skills. Along with it are the 2.1. Communication (5-items), 2.2. Leadership (5-items) and 2.3. Decision Making (5-items).

Part III is also a 5-point likert scale which is about Financial Management Skills and along with it are the 3.1. Budget / Financial Plan (5-items), 3.2. Audit / Financial Control (5-items), and 3.3. Financial Report (5-items).

Finally, the Part 4 which is the School Leadership that is composed of 4.1 Infrastructure (5-items), 4.2. Curriculum (5-items), 4.3. Academic Performance (5-items), 4.4. Funding (5-items), 4.5. Motivation (5-items) and 4.6. Professional Development (5-items).

The researcher was inspired by the idea of mixed-up models of Principal Instructional Management Scale designed by Hallinger (1982), the Principal Management Skills Survey Questionnaire utilized by the Nigerian researchers. Moreover, the questionnaire

Management Competency of School Heads: Basis for Effective and Improved School Leadership

has five descending from verbal interpretation or legend which started from 1.0-1.49 (Not Evident); 1.50-2.49 (Less Evident); 2.50-3.49 (Moderately Evident); 3.50-4.49 (Evident); and 4.50-5.0 (Highly Evident).

Validation of Instrument

The questionnaire, prior to final administration was subjected to validation whereby some questionnaire was modified to come up to a set of questionnaires from the framework became the basis of this research to maintain validity and reliability.

Data Collection Procedure

The mode of data gathering was with the use of survey questionnaire. Each of the respondents was given a structured set of questions in a Likert Scale format for gathering data perceived management competency and leadership skills of public elementary school heads in Lucena West Districts. Before gathering the data, the researcher asked permission from the Department of Education Schools Division of Lucena City to conduct the study. With the approval of the Division Superintendent and the school principals, the researcher administered the survey. The researcher collected the questionnaires from the respondents and tallied the data.

Ethical Consideration

In research, ethical considerations are a guide to specific conduct when gathering data from human participants with the purpose of protecting their rights as research participants. Ethical considerations include voluntary participation, informed consent, confidentiality of data collected from the respondents, protection from harm, and avoidance of plagiarism offenses [9]. All of the mentioned ethical considerations were strictly followed.

Statistical Analyses of Data

The data was tallied, tabulated, and analyzed statistically. In the breakdown of data, the following statistical tools will be applied.

The **Frequency** counting was the basic and first step in summing up the responses gathered in the survey.

Later, the **Percentage** was used to show the comparisons of the distribution of the respondents and the distribution of their responses in the specific subject or category. To find out the management competency needs of the school heads as self-reported by the teachers, **mean** was used also.

To determine the difference between the perceptions of teachers and school heads, the **T-Test** was carried out. A t-test will compare the means of two groups namely: the elementary grade teachers and school heads in Lucena West District.

The **Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient** (or Pearson correlation coefficient, for short) was employed by the researcher to measure the strength of a linear association between two variables. Through this, the researcher can attempt to draw a line of best fit through the data of two variables, and the Pearson correlation coefficient, r , indicates how far away all these data points are to this line of best fit.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Level of Management Competency

1.1 Instructional Skills

School's Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives (VMGO)

It can be drawn from table 2 that from the teachers' perception, the management competency of their school heads in instructional skills in terms of VMGO is evident based on the overall mean ($\bar{X}=4.38$) from all the indicators considered. The results suggest that teachers perceive evident that their school heads frames the school's VMGO in terms of teachers' responsibilities and uses data on learners' performance when developing such ($\bar{X}=4.41$), uses needs assessment and formal or informal methods to secure teachers' input on goal development ($\bar{X}=4.37$), communicates the school's mission effectively and develops goals that are easily understood and used by members of the school community ($\bar{X}=4.39$), refers to the school's academic goals when making curricular decisions with teachers and discusses them with teachers at faculty meetings ($\bar{X}=4.35$), and ensures that the school's academic goals are reflected in highly visible displays in the school ($\bar{X}=4.37$). While the school heads perceive that their management competency in instructional skills in terms of VMGO as highly evident ($\bar{X}=4.94$). This was manifested in all the indicators. From their perception, they frame the school's VMGO in terms of teachers' responsibilities and uses data on learners' performance when developing such ($\bar{X}=5.00$), uses needs assessment and formal or informal methods to secure teachers' input on goal development ($\bar{X}=5.00$), communicates the school's mission effectively and develops goals that are easily understood and used by members of the school community ($\bar{X}=4.90$), refers to the school's academic goals when making curricular decisions with teachers and discusses them with teachers at faculty meetings ($\bar{X}=4.80$), and ensures that the school's academic goals are reflected in highly visible displays in the school ($\bar{X}=5.00$).

Additionally, the findings are also in harmony with [10] who suggested that efficient school-based assessments give insight into what students know, what they can do, what they still need to learn, and where the school may make improvements.

Management Competency of School Heads: Basis for Effective and Improved School Leadership

Table 2. Perceived Level of Management Competency of School Heads in Instructional Skills in terms of School's VMGO

Indicators	Teacher		VI	School Head		VI
	Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
1. frames the school's VMGO in terms of teachers' responsibilities and uses data on learners' performance when developing such	4.41	0.65	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
2. uses needs assessment and formal or informal methods to secure teachers' input on goal development	4.37	0.65	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
3. communicates the school's mission effectively and develops goals that are easily understood and used by members of the school community	4.39	0.65	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
4. refers to the school's academic goals when making curricular decisions with teachers and discusses them with teachers at faculty meetings	4.35	0.67	Evident	4.80	0.42	Highly Evident
5. ensures that the school's academic goals are reflected in highly visible displays in the school (e.g., posters or bulletin boards emphasizing academic progress)	4.37	0.65	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
Overall	4.38	0.45	Evident	4.94	0.10	Highly Evident

Supervision and Evaluation

Table 3. reveals the teachers' and the school heads' perceived level of management competency of school heads in instructional skills in terms of supervision.

Indicators	Teacher		VI	School Head		VI
	Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
1. cooperate with teachers in defining objectives and ensure that classroom priorities are consistent with the goals and direction of the school	4.42	0.62	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
2. select learning experience method, procedures in achieving the objectives and assign teachers according to qualifications and competence	4.29	0.70	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
3. ensure that teachers in different units and work positions work cooperatively and not antagonistically for the common goals of the school	4.30	0.67	Evident	4.80	0.42	Highly Evident
4. supervise the teachers' instructional practices, provide post-observation feedback (e.g., in conferences or written evaluations), and evaluate planning and implementation of curriculum programs inside the classrooms	4.43	0.66	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
5. review and point out specific strengths and weaknesses in teachers and student work during classroom observations and evaluation in regular basis	4.30	0.67	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
Overall	4.35	0.44	Evident	4.92	0.14	Highly Evident

The teachers perceived the school heads' management competency in instructional skills in terms of supervision and evaluation as evident ($\bar{X}=4.35$). the teachers perceive that the school heads cooperate with teachers in defining objectives and ensure that classroom priorities are consistent with the goals and direction of the school ($\bar{X}=4.42$), select learning experience method, procedures in achieving the objectives and assign teachers according to qualifications and competence ($\bar{X}=4.29$), ensure that teachers in different units and work positions work cooperatively and not antagonistically for the common goals of the school (4.30), supervise the teachers' instructional practices, provide post-observation feedback (e.g., in conferences or written evaluations), and evaluate planning and implementation of curriculum programs inside the classrooms ($\bar{X}=4.43$), and review and point out specific strengths and weaknesses in teachers and student work during classroom observations and evaluation in regular basis ($\bar{X}=4.30$).

The school heads perceived their management competency in instructional skills in terms of supervision and evaluation as highly evident ($\bar{X}=4.92$). All indicators also manifested highly evident. From the school heads' perception, the school heads cooperate with teachers in defining objectives and ensure that classroom priorities are consistent with the goals and direction of the school ($\bar{X}=5.00$), select learning experience method, procedures in achieving the objectives and assign teachers according to qualifications and competence ($\bar{X}=4.90$), ensure that teachers in different units and work positions work cooperatively and not antagonistically for the

Management Competency of School Heads: Basis for Effective and Improved School Leadership

common goals of the school (4.80), supervise the teachers' instructional practices, provide post-observation feedback (e.g., in conferences or written evaluations), and evaluate planning and implementation of curriculum programs inside the classrooms (\bar{X} =5.00), and review and point out specific strengths and weaknesses in teachers and student work during classroom observations and evaluation in regular basis (\bar{X} =4.90).

Table 3: Perceived Level of Management Competency of School Heads in Instructional Skills in terms of Supervision and Evaluation
Supervision in education is a professional skill in helping and guiding teachers as the ultimate end to increase opportunity and the capacity of schools to contribute more effectively to the learning of students. The findings reveal that the school heads efficiently and effectively provide supervision and evaluation based on the teachers' and the school heads' perception. These findings adhere to the idea of Stremmel [11]. According to him, pedagogical leadership has a connection to students' learning as well as the development of teachers' skills and the values and viewpoints on education. This also means that the school heads recognize these essential functions of a school head.

Curriculum Coordination

It can be deduced from table 4 that the management competency of school heads in instructional skills in terms of curricular coordination is evident from the teachers' perception (\bar{X} =4.32). The teachers perceive that the school heads make clear who is responsible for coordinating the curriculum across grade levels and monitor the classroom curriculum to see that it covers the school's curricular objectives (\bar{X} =4.37), draw upon the results of school-wide testing when making curricular decisions through active participation in the review of curricular materials (\bar{X} =4.20), interpret findings of educational research, apply the conclusions in solving the educational problems, innovate and support experimental practices which promote innovation and change in the school's curriculum and instruction (\bar{X} =4.31), identify and understand the implications of political, economic, and social trends for the development of the educational program (\bar{X} =4.38), and assist teachers to plan, to implement and to evaluate measures, to assess the overlap between the school's curricular objectives and the school's achievement tests for the improvement of teaching practice (\bar{X} =4.32).

The management competency of school heads in instructional skills in terms of curricular coordination is highly evident (\bar{X} =4.86) based on the school heads' perception. They perception say that they make clear who is responsible for coordinating the curriculum across grade levels and monitor the classroom curriculum to see that it covers the school's curricular objectives (\bar{X} =4.90), draw upon the results of school-wide testing when making curricular decisions through active participation in the review of curricular materials (\bar{X} =4.80), interpret findings of educational research, apply the conclusions in solving the educational problems, innovate and support experimental practices which promote innovation and change in the school's curriculum and instruction (\bar{X} =4.70), identify and understand the implications of political, economic, and social trends for the development of the educational program (\bar{X} =4.90), and assist teachers to plan, to implement and to evaluate measures, to assess the overlap between the school's curricular objectives and the school's achievement tests for the improvement of teaching practice (\bar{X} =5.00).

Staff development programs for teachers are a crucial component of a successful competence-based curriculum implementation strategy. In addition, the issue of school-based assessment was discovered to have a significant role to play in the school achievement following competence-based curriculum adoption [12]. These important aspects in curricular coordination in the schools are evident based on the perception of the teachers and the school heads.

Table 4. Perceived Level of Management Competency of School Heads in Instructional Skills in terms of Curricular Coordination

Indicators	Teacher		VI	School Head		VI
	Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
1. make clear who is responsible for coordinating the curriculum across grade levels and monitor the classroom curriculum to see that it covers the school's curricular objectives	4.37	0.63	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
2. draw upon the results of school-wide testing when making curricular decisions through active participation in the review of curricular materials	4.20	0.64	Evident	4.80	0.42	Highly Evident
3. interpret findings of educational research, apply the conclusions in solving the educational problems, innovate and support experimental practices which promote innovation and change in the school's curriculum and instruction	4.31	0.63	Evident	4.70	0.48	Highly Evident
4. identify and understand the implications of political, economic, and social trends for the development of the educational program	4.38	0.65	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
5. assist teachers to plan, to implement and to evaluate measures, to assess the overlap between the school's	4.32	0.62	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident

Management Competency of School Heads: Basis for Effective and Improved School Leadership

curricular objectives and the school's achievement tests for the improvement of teaching practice						
Overall	4.32	0.41	Evident	4.86	0.19	Highly Evident

Student Progress

It can be deduced from table 5 that the management competency of school heads in instructional skills in terms of student progress is evident ($\bar{X}=4.36$) based on the perception of the teachers. This is also evident in all the indicators. According to the teachers, the school heads meet individually with teachers to discuss student progress ($\bar{X}=4.36$), discuss academic performance results with the faculty to identify curricular ($\bar{X}=4.24$), use tests and other performance measure to assess progress toward school goals (4.39), inform teachers at the school's performance results in written form ($\bar{X}=4.47$), and inform learners of school's academic progress ($\bar{X}=4.35$).

From the school heads' perspective, their management competency in instructional skills in terms of student progress is highly evident ($\bar{X}=4.94$). This was also manifested in all the indicators. According to them, the school heads meet individually with teachers to discuss student progress ($\bar{X}=5.00$), discuss academic performance results with the faculty to identify curricular ($\bar{X}=4.90$), use tests and other performance measure to assess progress toward school goals ($\bar{X}=4.90$), inform teachers at the school's performance results in written form ($\bar{X}=4.90$), and inform learners of school's academic progress ($\bar{X}=5.00$).

Assessment not only helps to identify a student's need for remediation, but also helps to raise the quality of instruction [13]. Additionally, effective school-based assessment enables a school to frequently change its evaluation modalities. A school can more quickly reach its objective when teachers use activities in the classroom, like daily observations, periodic quizzes, and standardized tests. School-based assessment was also observed as a crucial component of both teaching and learning, and it is widely acknowledged as an indicator of high-quality teaching and learning is widely acknowledged

Table 5. Perceived Level of Management Competency of School Heads in Instructional Skills in terms of Student Progr

Indicators	Teacher		VI	School Head		VI
	Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
1. meet individually with teachers to discuss student progress	4.36	0.69	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
2. discuss academic performance results with the faculty to identify curricular	4.24	0.68	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
3. use tests and other performance measure to assess progress toward school goals	4.39	0.67	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
4. inform teachers at the school's performance results in written form (e.g., in a memo or newsletter)	4.47	0.69	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
5. inform learners of school's academic progress	4.35	0.63	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
Overall	4.36	0.49	Evident	4.94	0.10	Highly Evident

Instructional Time

Table 6 shows the perception of teachers on the management competency of school heads in instructional skills in terms of instructional time. From their perception, the management competency of school heads is evident ($\bar{X}=4.37$). This is also evident in all the indicators. According to them, the school heads limit interruptions of instructional time by public address announcements ($\bar{X}=4.26$), ensure that learners are not called to the office during instructional time ($\bar{X}=4.42$), ensure that tardy and truant learners suffer specific consequences for missing instructional time ($\bar{X}=4.39$), encourage teachers to use instructional time for teaching and practicing new skills and concepts ($\bar{X}=4.36$), and limit the intrusion of extra- and co-curricular activities on instructional time ($\bar{X}=4.43$).

The perception of the school heads about their level of management competency is highly evident ($\bar{X}=4.86$). The same level is manifested in all the indicators. According to their perception, the school heads limit interruptions of instructional time by public address announcements ($\bar{X}=4.70$), ensure that learners are not called to the office during instructional time ($\bar{X}=4.80$), ensure that tardy and truant learners suffer specific consequences for missing instructional time ($\bar{X}=4.80$), encourage teachers to use instructional time for teaching and practicing new skills and concepts ($\bar{X}=5.00$), and limit the intrusion of extra- and co-curricular activities on instructional time ($\bar{X}=5.00$).

These were anchored to the importance and essential elements of managing instructional time. School heads can create an organization that is continuously developing the social capital that allows people to trust, depend on, and learn from each other.

Management Competency of School Heads: Basis for Effective and Improved School Leadership

Table 6. Perceived Level of Management Competency of School Heads in Instructional Skills in terms of Instructional Time

Indicators	Teacher		VI	School Head		VI
	Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
1. limit interruptions of instructional time by public address announcements	4.26	0.72	Evident	4.70	0.48	Highly Evident
2. ensure that learners are not called to the office during instructional time	4.42	0.64	Evident	4.80	0.42	Highly Evident
3. ensure that tardy and truant learners suffer specific consequences for missing instructional time	4.39	0.65	Evident	4.80	0.42	Highly Evident
4. encourage teachers to use instructional time for teaching and practicing new skills and concepts	4.36	0.77	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
5. limit the intrusion of extra- and co-curricular activities on instructional time	4.43	0.59	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
Overall	4.37	0.40	Evident	4.86	0.16	Highly Evident

Visibility

It can be deduced from table 7 that the level of management competency of school heads in instructional skills in terms of visibility is evident ($\bar{X}=4.41$) from the teachers' perception. The same level is manifested in all the indicators. Based on the teachers' perception, the school heads take time to talk informally with learners and teachers during recess and breaks ($\bar{X}=4.34$), visit classrooms to discuss school issues with teachers and learners ($\bar{X}=4.39$), attend/participate in extra- and co-curricular activities ($\bar{X}=4.48$), cover classes for teachers until a late or substitute teacher arrives ($\bar{X}=4.41$), and teach learners or provides direct instruction to classes ($\bar{X}=4.44$).

The management competency of school heads in instructional skills in terms of visibility as perceived by the school heads is high evident ($\bar{X}=4.94$). According to their perception, they take time to talk informally with learners and teachers during recess and breaks ($\bar{X}=4.90$), visit classrooms to discuss school issues with teachers and learners ($\bar{X}=4.90$), attend/participate in extra- and co-curricular activities ($\bar{X}=5.00$), cover classes for teachers until a late or substitute teacher arrives ($\bar{X}=5.00$), and teach learners or provides direct instruction to classes ($\bar{X}=4.90$).

Quality education depends in part on having sufficient time for teaching and learning. Schools need an adequate number of days and hours for instruction and well-trained teachers to deliver quality lessons, so that student engagement and learning is maximized [14]. The findings reveal that the school heads foster adequate to strict instructional time in their schools based on the perception of the teachers and the school heads.

Table 7. Perceived Level of Management Competency of School Heads in Instructional Skills in terms of Visibility

Indicators	Teacher		VI	School Head		VI
	Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
1. take time to talk informally with learners and teachers during recess and breaks	4.34	0.71	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
2. visit classrooms to discuss school issues with teachers and learners	4.39	0.65	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
3. attend/participate in extra- and co-curricular activities	4.48	0.64	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
4. cover classes for teachers until a late or substitute teacher arrives	4.41	0.70	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
5. teach learners or provides direct instruction to classes	4.44	0.64	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
Overall	4.41	0.41	Evident	4.94	0.13	Highly Evident

Incentives for Teachers

It can be deduced from table 8 that the level of management competency of school heads in instructional skills in terms of incentives for teachers is evident ($\bar{X}=4.45$) based on the overall perception of teachers. The teachers perceive that the school heads reinforce superior performance by teachers in staff meetings, newsletters, and/or memos ($\bar{X}=4.27$), compliment teachers privately for their efforts or performance ($\bar{X}=4.39$), acknowledge teachers' exceptional performance by writing memos for their personnel files ($\bar{X}=4.59$), reward special efforts by teachers with opportunities for professional recognition ($\bar{X}=4.53$), and create professional growth opportunities for teachers as a reward for special contributions to the school ($\bar{X}=4.45$).

The perception of the school heads on the level of their management competency in instructional skills in terms of incentive for teachers is highly evident ($\bar{X}=4.92$). This is also manifested in all the indicators. According to their perception, they reinforce superior performance by teachers in staff meetings, newsletters, and/or memos ($\bar{X}=4.90$), compliment teachers privately for their

Management Competency of School Heads: Basis for Effective and Improved School Leadership

efforts or performance (4.90), acknowledge teachers' exceptional performance by writing memos for their personnel files (\bar{X} =4.90), reward special efforts by teachers with opportunities for professional recognition (\bar{X} =4.90), and create professional growth opportunities for teachers as a reward for special contributions to the school (\bar{X} =5.00).

The findings from the study reveal to be in harmony with the Equity Theory of Motivation, which states that positive outcomes and high levels of motivation can be expected only when employees perceive their treatment to be fair.

Table 8: Perceived Level of Management Competency of School Heads in Instructional Skills in terms of Incentives for Teachers

Indicators	Teacher		VI	School Head		VI
	Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
1. reinforce superior performance by teachers in staff meetings, newsletters, and/or memos	4.27	0.74	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
2. compliment teachers privately for their efforts or performance	4.39	0.65	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
3. acknowledge teachers' exceptional performance by writing memos for their personnel files	4.59	0.57	Highly Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
4. reward special efforts by teachers with opportunities for professional recognition	4.53	0.64	Highly Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
5. create professional growth opportunities for teachers as a reward for special contributions to the school	4.45	0.58	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
Overall	4.45	0.41	Evident	4.92	0.17	Highly Evident

Incentives for Learning

It can be drawn from table 9, from the teachers' perception, that the level of management competency of school heads in instructional skill in terms of incentives for learning is evident based on the overall mean (\bar{X} =4.44). The teachers perceived that the school heads recognize students who do superior work with formal rewards such as an honor roll or mention in the school newsletter (\bar{X} =4.33), use assemblies to honor students for academic accomplishments or for behavior or citizenship (\bar{X} =4.36), recognize superior student achievement or improvement by seeing in the office the students with their work (\bar{X} =4.56), contact parents to communicate improved or exemplary learners' performance or contributions (\bar{X} =4.46), and support teachers actively in their recognition and/or reward of learners' contributions to and accomplishments in class (\bar{X} =4.48).

Incentives for learning refer to a typically created by a school head to give to his/her people a sort of verbal rewards for their commendable work behaviors. Incentives for learning are a form of *inducement or supplemental reward that serves as a motivational device for intended learning*. According to the findings, the school heads ensure to provide incentives for learning in their schools as perceived by the teachers and the school heads themselves.

Table 9. Perceived Level of Management Competency of School Heads in Instructional Skills in terms of Incentives for Learning

Indicators	Teacher		VI	School Head		VI
	Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
1. recognize students who do superior work with formal rewards such as an honor roll or mention in the school newsletter	4.33	0.71	Evident	4.80	0.42	Highly Evident
2. use assemblies to honor students for academic accomplishments or for behavior or citizenship	4.36	0.67	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
3. recognize superior student achievement or improvement by seeing in the office the students with their work	4.56	0.56	Highly Evident	4.80	0.42	Highly Evident
4. contact parents to communicate improved or exemplary learners' performance or contributions	4.46	0.67	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
5. support teachers actively in their recognition and/or reward of learners' contributions to and accomplishments in class	4.48	0.59	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
Overall	4.44	0.41	Evident	4.86	0.25	Highly Evident

Career Motivations

It can be deduced from table 10 that the level of management competency in instructional skills in terms of career motivation based on the teachers' perception is evident (\bar{X} =4.45). This was manifested in all the indicators. Based on the results, the teachers perceive

Management Competency of School Heads: Basis for Effective and Improved School Leadership

that the school heads assign duties to teachers according to their interests and choices enhances their performance and effectiveness ($\bar{X}=4.50$), provide ample chances for teachers' professional growth and individual abilities which help boosting performance and effectiveness in their careers ($\bar{X}=4.39$), motivate self-study for professional growth among teachers improves their effectiveness and performance ($\bar{X}=4.43$), give token or rewards and incentives to teachers for extra work done to perform better and effectively in their various functions (highly evident), and trust the teachers' abilities to achieve desired goals and recommend them on time for promotion which enhances their performance in their teaching functions ($\bar{X}=4.41$).

From the school heads' perspective, the level of their management competency in instructional skills in terms of career motivation is highly evident ($\bar{X}=4.98$). This is all manifested in all the indicators. According to them, they assign duties to teachers according to their interests and choices enhances their performance and effectiveness ($\bar{X}=5.00$), provide ample chances for teachers' professional growth and individual abilities which help boosting performance and effectiveness in their careers ($\bar{X}=5.00$), motivate self-study for professional growth among teachers improves their effectiveness and performance ($\bar{X}=4.90$), give token or rewards and incentives to teachers for extra work done to perform better and effectively in their various functions ($\bar{X}=5.00$), and trust the teachers' abilities to achieve desired goals and recommend them on time for promotion which enhances their performance in their teaching functions ($\bar{X}=5.00$).

Career motivation which refers to the satisfier or motivating factors, such as includes achievement, recognition, responsibility, and advancement – all related to the job contentment and rewards from work performance is an important factor at work that help keeps teachers does their work effectively. These factors are all evident as perceived both by the teachers and the school heads.

Table 10. Perceived Level of Management Competency of School Heads in Instructional Skills in terms of Career Motivation

Indicators	Teacher		VI	School Head		VI
	Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
1. assign duties to teachers according to their interests and choices enhances their performance and effectiveness	4.50	0.63	Highly Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
2. provide ample chances for teachers' professional growth and individual abilities which help boosting performance and effectiveness in their careers	4.39	0.65	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
3. motivate self-study for professional growth among teachers improves their effectiveness and performance	4.43	0.70	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
4. give token or rewards and incentives to teachers for extra work done to perform better and effectively in their various functions	4.52	0.58	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
5. trust the teachers' abilities to achieve desired goals and recommend them on time for promotion which enhances their performance in their teaching functions	4.41	0.60	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
Overall	4.45	0.44	Evident	4.98	0.06	Highly Evident

Professional Development

Table 11 reveals the overall level of management competency of school heads in instructional skills in terms of professional development as evident ($\bar{X}=4.44$). Based on the teachers, the school heads ensure that in-service activities, trainings, workshops, or seminars attended facilitates experience and professional growth towards achieving school goals ($\bar{X}=4.27$), set aside time at faculty meetings for teachers to share ideas or information from in-service activities ($\bar{X}=4.42$), support teachers to prepare different instructional materials on teaching-learning process ($\bar{X}=4.55$), give piece of advice for teachers to conduct action research and facilitate short term training to teachers on new teaching methodologies ($\bar{X}=4.48$), and give piece of advice for teachers to use model effective teaching methods and encourage them to motivate learners in the classroom ($\bar{X}=4.46$).

The school heads' perception their level of management competency in instructional skills in terms of professional development is highly evident based on the overall mean rating ($\bar{X}=4.80$). This is also manifested in all the indicators. Based on their perception, the school heads the school heads ensure that in-service activities, trainings, workshops, or seminars attended facilitates experience and professional growth towards achieving school goals ($\bar{X}=4.80$), set aside time at faculty meetings for teachers to share ideas or information from in-service activities ($\bar{X}=4.70$), support teachers to prepare different instructional materials on teaching-learning process ($\bar{X}=4.60$), give piece of advice for teachers to conduct action research and facilitate short term training to teachers on new teaching methodologies ($\bar{X}=5.00$), and give piece of advice for teachers to use model effective teaching methods and encourage them to motivate learners in the classroom ($\bar{X}=4.90$).

Professional development is the intensive, comprehensive, and supported initiative centered on improving the effectiveness of both teachers and principals to ultimately have a positive impact on student outcomes. Based on the findings, professional development is evidently implemented in the schools by the school heads as perceived both by the teachers and the school heads.

Management Competency of School Heads: Basis for Effective and Improved School Leadership

Table 11. Perceived Level of Management Competency of School Heads in Instructional Skills in terms of Professional Development

Indicators	Teacher		VI	School Head		VI
	Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
1. ensure that in-service activities, trainings, workshops, or seminars attended facilitates experience and professional growth towards achieving school goals	4.27	0.76	Evident	4.80	0.42	Highly Evident
2. set aside time at faculty meetings for teachers to share ideas or information from in-service activities	4.42	0.65	Evident	4.70	0.48	Highly Evident
3. support teachers to prepare different instructional materials on teaching-learning process	4.55	0.63	Highly Evident	4.60	0.52	Highly Evident
4. give piece of advice for teachers to conduct action research and facilitate short term training to teachers on new teaching methodologies	4.48	0.64	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
5. give piece of advice for teachers to use model effective teaching methods and encourage them to motivate learners in the classroom	4.46	0.59	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
Overall	4.44	0.44	Evident	4.80	0.21	Highly Evident

1.2 Personnel Skills

Communication

It can be deduced from table 12 based on the teachers' perception that the level of management competency of school heads in personnel skills in terms of communication is evident ($\bar{X}=4.34$). The same level of competency is manifested in all the indicators. Based on the teachers' perception, the school heads communicate effectively with teachers through praising in public and criticizes in private; hence mold those who have differing philosophies, experiences, and approaches into effective working team members ($\bar{X}=4.38$), delegate duties and authorities to capable teachers, recognize their talents and assist them in formulating purpose and accepting responsibility ($\bar{X}=4.31$), supervise teachers to ensure that decisions are implemented, and duties are performed ($\bar{X}=4.36$), and guide and direct teachers' meetings and maintain participant's interest, involvement as well as defusing tense situations and negotiates solution ($\bar{X}=4.38$).

From the school heads' perception, their overall level of management competency in personnel skills in terms of communication is highly evident ($\bar{X}=4.94$) and is also manifested in all the indicators. Their perception reveal that they, as school heads, communicate effectively with teachers through praising in public and criticizes in private; hence mold those who have differing philosophies, experiences, and approaches into effective working team members ($\bar{X}=4.90$), delegate duties and authorities to capable teachers, recognize their talents and assist them in formulating purpose and accepting responsibility ($\bar{X}=5.00$), supervise teachers to ensure that decisions are implemented, and duties are performed ($\bar{X}=5.00$), and guide and direct teachers' meetings and maintain participant's interest, involvement as well as defusing tense situations and negotiates solution ($\bar{X}=5.00$).

Communication is the ability to convey the message effectively to subordinates. It is needed by the school heads in communicating knowledge, instructions, purpose, goal, mission, and vision of his/her school. The findings of the study reveal that the school heads have effective communication ability as perceived by the teachers and the school heads.

Table 12. Perceived Level of Management Competency of School Heads in Personnel Skills in terms of Communication

Indicators	Teacher		VI	School Head		VI
	Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
1. communicate effectively with teachers through praising in public and criticizes in private; hence mold those who have differing philosophies, experiences, and approaches into effective working team members	4.38	0.62	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
2. delegate duties and authorities to capable teachers, recognize their talents and assist them in formulating purpose and accepting responsibility	4.31	0.66	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
3. supervise teachers to ensure that decisions are implemented, and duties are performed	4.26	0.69	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
4. identify the needs, create the conditions for the continued professional development of teachers	4.36	0.67	Evident	4.80	0.42	Highly Evident
5. guide and direct teachers' meetings and maintain participant's interest, involvement as well as defusing tense situations and negotiates solution	4.38	0.66	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
Overall	4.34	0.43	Evident	4.94	0.13	Highly Evident

Management Competency of School Heads: Basis for Effective and Improved School Leadership

Leadership

It can be drawn from table 13 that the level of management competency of school heads in personnel skills in terms of leadership is evident ($\bar{X}=4.42$) based on the overall perception of the teachers. The teachers perceive their school heads who allot duties to teachers according to their choices and interests and allow them to take freedom of action ($\bar{X}=4.24$), give verbal and nonverbal recognition to the teachers and place teachers on jobs in which their individual potentials can be fully utilized ($\bar{X}=4.41$), show special interest on teachers who have medical challenges and health conditions ($\bar{X}=4.58$), and consult teachers in critical decision-making processes in the school ($\bar{X}=4.47$).

The school heads perceived their level of management competency in personnel skill in terms of leadership as highly evident ($\bar{X}=4.9$) based on the overall rating. This is also manifested in all the indicators. The school heads' perceive that they allot duties to teachers according to their choices and interests and allow them to take freedom of action ($\bar{X}=4.80$), give verbal and nonverbal recognition to the teachers and place teachers on jobs in which their individual potentials can be fully utilized ($\bar{X}=4.90$), show special interest on teachers who have medical challenges and health conditions ($\bar{X}=4.90$), and consult teachers in critical decision-making processes in the school ($\bar{X}=5.00$).

Educational leadership is a collaborative process that unites the talents and forces of teachers, students, and parents to improve the quality of education. The study reveals that the school heads provide evident school leadership based as perceived by the teachers and the school heads.

Table 13. Perceived Level of Management Competency of School Heads in Personnel Skills in terms of Leadership

Indicators	Teacher		VI	School Head		VI
	Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
1. allot duties to teachers according to their choices and interests and allow them to take freedom of action	4.24	0.73	Evident	4.80	0.42	Highly Evident
2. give verbal and nonverbal recognition to the teachers and place teachers on jobs in which their individual potentials can be fully utilized	4.41	0.62	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
3. show special interest on teachers who have medical challenges and health conditions	4.58	0.57	Highly Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
4. consult teachers in critical decision-making processes in the school	4.47	0.69	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
Overall	4.42	0.41	Evident	4.9	0.14	Highly Evident

Decision-Making

It can be deduced from table 14 that the teachers' perception on the level of management competency of school heads in personnel skills in terms of decision making based on the overall rating is evident ($\bar{X}=4.36$). This level is also manifested in all the indicators. The perception of the teachers reveals that the school heads identify and manage the force operating within the group decision making situation ($\bar{X}=4.35$), synthesize ideas and information from the variety of sources ($\bar{X}=4.27$), translate policies into effective action ($\bar{X}=4.40$), facilitate shared decision making among members and mobilize people to make a contribution ($\bar{X}=4.37$), and elicit the support, and maintain the interest of members ($\bar{X}=4.40$).

Decision-making is *the act of deciding something especially with a group of people*. It is one of the most important activities of school heads that they engage daily at all levels of a school organization. Without decision making any kind of function is not possible. Study show that the school heads evidently deliver decision-making in their schools as perceived by the teachers and the school heads.

Table 14. Perceived Level of Management Competency of School Heads in Personnel Skills in terms of Decision-Making

Indicators	Teacher		VI	School Head		VI
	Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
1. identify and manage the force operating within the group decision making situation	4.35	0.69	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
2. synthesize ideas and information from the variety of sources	4.27	0.66	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
3. translate policies into effective action	4.40	0.65	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
4. facilitate shared decision making among members and mobilize people to make a contribution	4.37	0.66	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
5. elicit the support, and maintain the interest of members	4.40	0.64	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
Overall	4.36	0.46	Evident	4.96	0.13	Highly Evident

Management Competency of School Heads: Basis for Effective and Improved School Leadership

1.3 Financial Skills

Budget / Financial Plan

Table 15 reveals the perception of the teachers about the level of management competency of school heads in personnel skills in terms of budget/financial plan. According to the overall rating of the teachers, the level of competency of the school heads in this skill is evident ($\bar{X}=4.33$). The same level is manifested in all the specific indicators. The teachers perceive that the school heads study, analyze and learn how to analyze income and expenditure on monthly basis ($\bar{X}=4.38$), learn how to count down expenditure ($\bar{X}=4.29$), learn how to avoid excessive spending ($\bar{X}=4.30$), identify and supervise the maintenance requirements of buildings, equipment, and grounds ($\bar{X}=4.38$), and develop, prepare, present, and administer school budgets ($\bar{X}=4.30$).

The overall mean rating reveals a highly evident ($\bar{X}=4.80$) level of management competency in personnel skills in terms of budget/financial plan. It is also manifested in all the specific indicators. The school heads perceive that they analyze and learn how to analyze income and expenditure on monthly basis ($\bar{X}=4.60$), learn how to count down expenditure (4.50), learn how to avoid excessive spending ($\bar{X}=5.00$), identify, and supervise the maintenance requirements of buildings, equipment, and grounds ($\bar{X}=5.00$), and develop, prepare, present, and administer school budgets ($\bar{X}=4.90$).

To ensure effective financial management in schools, It is deemed it is important that there is proper participation of stakeholders in budget drafting processes, developing, preparing, presenting, and administering of the school budgets.. The budgeting or financial planning preparation should involve parents, learners, and educators of schools to have an analysis of income on monthly basis, which can only be successful because of appropriate dissemination of information to all stakeholders [15].

Table 15. Perceived Level of Management Competency of School Heads in Personnel Skills in terms of Budget or Financial Plan

Indicators	Teacher		VI	School Head		VI
	Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
1. study, analyze and learn how to analyze income and expenditure on monthly basis	4.38	0.65	Evident	4.60	0.52	Highly Evident
2. learn how to count down expenditure	4.29	0.70	Evident	4.50	0.53	Highly Evident
3. learn how to avoid excessive spending	4.30	0.67	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
4. identify and supervise the maintenance requirements of buildings, equipment, and grounds	4.38	0.71	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
5. develop, prepare, present, and administer school budgets	4.30	0.69	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
Overall	4.33	0.48	Evident	4.80	0.21	Highly Evident

Audit/Financial Control

It can be deduced from table 16 that the level of management competency of school heads in personnel skills in terms of audit/financial control is evident from the teachers' perception. The same level of competency is also manifested in all the indicators. From the teachers' perspective, the school heads detect financial error ($\bar{X}=4.24$), enable to determine their gains and losses in schools ($\bar{X}=4.37$), know immediately the actual financial position of the school ($\bar{X}=4.51$), and arrange for the selection procurement, storage, distribution and perpetual inventory of material resources and equipment ($\bar{X}=4.49$).

From the perception of the school heads, it shows that their level of competency in this skill is highly evident (5.00). This is also manifested in all the indicators. They perceive that they detect financial error ($\bar{X}=4.80$), enable to determine their gains and losses in schools ($\bar{X}=4.80$), know immediately the actual financial position of the school ($\bar{X}=4.60$), and arrange for the selection procurement, storage, distribution and perpetual inventory of material resources and equipment ($\bar{X}=4.90$).

It also assumed that sound financial control is a vital function of effective and efficient financial management in schools ensure effective and efficient school financial management, including budgetary control, asset control, the management of stock and the management of cash [17].

Table 16. Perceived Level of Management Competency of School Heads in Personnel Skills in terms of Audit or Financial Control

Indicators	Teacher		VI	School Head		VI
	Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
1. detect financial error	4.24	0.74	Evident	4.80	0.42	Highly Evident
2. enable to determine their gains and losses in schools	4.37	0.68	Evident	4.80	0.42	Highly Evident
3. know immediately the actual financial position of the school	4.51	0.66	Highly Evident	4.60	0.52	Highly Evident
4. arrange for the selection procurement, storage, distribution and perpetual inventory of material resources and equipment	4.49	0.64	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident

Management Competency of School Heads: Basis for Effective and Improved School Leadership

Overall	4.41	0.64	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
----------------	------	------	---------	------	------	----------------

Financial Report

It can be gleaned from table 17 that the level of management competency of school heads in personnel skills in terms of financial report is evident ($\bar{X}=4.36$) based on the teachers' overall perception. The same level of perception is manifested on all the indicators. The teachers perceive that the school heads know how to report income and expenditure on quarterly basis and to structure reports in accordance with the responsibility areas ($\bar{X}=4.35$), acquire skills on comparing budgeting items with its expenditures and know that skills of totaling each column in financial reporting are essential ($\bar{X}=4.30$), develop and maintain an efficient system of record keeping and know that prompt compilation and submission of financial report is imperative for them ($\bar{X}=4.36$), acquire the skills of balancing the check books to agree with the cash balance on the report ($\bar{X}=4.36$), and evaluate the effectiveness of the school's physical resources for meeting the needs of the educational program ($\bar{X}=4.38$).

From the school heads' perception, they perceive that their level of management competency in personnel skills in terms of financial report is highly evident ($\bar{X}=4.92$). According to their perception, they know how to report income and expenditure on quarterly basis and to structure reports in accordance with the responsibility areas ($\bar{X}=4.90$), acquire skills on comparing budgeting items with its expenditures and know that skills of totaling each column in financial reporting are essential ($\bar{X}=4.90$), develop and maintain an efficient system of record keeping and know that prompt compilation and submission of financial report is imperative for them ($\bar{X}=4.90$), acquire the skills of balancing the check books to agree with the cash balance on the report ($\bar{X}=4.90$), and evaluate the effectiveness of the school's physical resources for meeting the needs of the educational program ($\bar{X}=5.00$).

Financial reporting is an essential part of managing finances of the school because it keeps the records of the expenses of the school. As perceived by the teachers and the school heads, it is evident that financial reports are effectively done by the school heads. It was suggested that school head should send a summary of their schools' financial positions to parents and relevant stakeholders every term to update them on the financial situations of the schools [18].

Table 17. Perceived Level of Management Competency of School Heads in Personnel Skills in terms of Financial Report

Indicators	Teacher		VI	School Head		VI
	Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
1. know how to report income and expenditure on quarterly basis and to structure reports in accordance with the responsibility areas	4.35	0.67	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
2. acquire skills on comparing budgeting items with its expenditures and know that skills of totaling each column in financial reporting are essential	4.30	0.66	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
3. develop and maintain an efficient system of record keeping and know that prompt compilation and submission of financial report is imperative for them	4.36	0.67	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
4. acquire the skills of balancing the check books to agree with the cash balance on the report	4.36	0.66	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
5. evaluate the effectiveness of the school's physical resources for meeting the needs of the educational program	4.38	0.66	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
Overall	4.35	0.47	Evident	4.92	0.19	Highly Evident

1.4 School Leadership

Infrastructure

It can be deduced from table 18 that the school heads' level of school leadership in terms of infrastructure is evident ($\bar{X}=4.32$) based on the overall perception of the teachers. The same level of competence is manifested in all the indicators. The teachers perceive that the school heads ensure that school should be insured for fire, flood and earthquakes and considers quick type of insurance ($\bar{X}=4.39$), establish communication and coordination among government agencies, designers, builders, and operators ($\bar{X}=4.29$), use the school as a multi-purpose, cultural utility that provides resources and services to the wider community; henceforth, establish clear rules about the use of shared public/private spaces and facility for educational, cultural, and recreational opportunities for learners ($\bar{X}=4.22$), operate the school as a sustainable and resilient system, incorporate data collection, monitor school curriculum, and consider planning of the educational infrastructure to optimize use of resources ($\bar{X}=4.38$), and create agricultural grounds and gardens as classroom extensions and to generate vocational opportunities for students and teach them about commerce and support food security ($\bar{X}=4.32$).

The school heads perceived their level in school leadership in terms of infrastructure as highly evident ($\bar{X}=4.96$). Based on the results, the school heads ensure that school should be insured for fire, flood and earthquakes and considers quick type of insurance

Management Competency of School Heads: Basis for Effective and Improved School Leadership

develop emergency plans in the event of a major disaster and communicate/coordinate among government agencies, designers, builders, and operators ($\bar{X}=4.90$), establish communication and coordination among government agencies, designers, builders, and operators, use the school as a multi-purpose, cultural utility that provides resources and services to the wider community. Henceforth, establish clear rules about the use of shared public/private spaces and facility for educational, cultural, and recreational opportunities for learners ($\bar{X}=5.00$), operate the school as a sustainable and resilient system, incorporate data collection, monitor school curriculum, and consider planning of the educational infrastructure to optimize use of resources ($\bar{X}=4.90$), operate the school as a sustainable and resilient system, incorporate data collection, monitor school curriculum, and consider planning of the educational infrastructure to optimize use of resources ($\bar{X}=5.00$), and create agricultural grounds and gardens as classroom extensions and to generate vocational opportunities for students and teach them about commerce and support food security ($\bar{X}=5.00$). The findings of the study show that the leadership of the school heads in terms of infrastructure is evidently effective as perceived by the teachers and the school heads. Infrastructure standards, as outlined, there are the four standards of Child Friendly Schools Infrastructure that are expected to be met by all schools [19].

Table 18. Perceived Level of School Heads in School Leadership in terms of Infrastructure

Indicators	Teacher		VI	School Head		VI
	Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
1. ensure that school should be insured for fire, flood and earthquakes and considers quick type of insurance, develop emergency plans in the event of a major disaster and communicate/coordinate among government agencies, designers, builders, and operators	4.39	0.63	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
2. establish communication and coordination among government agencies, designers, builders, and operators	4.29	0.69	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
3. use the school as a multi-purpose, cultural utility that provides resources and services to the wider community; henceforth, establish clear rules about the use of shared public/private spaces and facility for educational, cultural, and recreational opportunities for learners	4.22	0.69	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
4. operate the school as a sustainable and resilient system, incorporate data collection, monitor school curriculum, and consider planning of the educational infrastructure to optimize use of resources	4.38	0.69	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
5. create agricultural grounds and gardens as classroom extensions and to generate vocational opportunities for students and teach them about commerce and support food security	4.32	0.65	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
Overall Mean	4.32	0.46	Evident	4.96	0.13	Highly Evident

Curriculum

It can be deduced from table 19 that the level of school leadership of school heads in terms of curriculum is evident ($\bar{X}=4.42$) from the teachers' overall perception. The teachers perceive that school heads assist teachers in lesson planning, developing/selecting instructional materials, in evaluating student performance, and advise them about new developments in teaching ($\bar{X}=4.24$), help teachers to evaluate curricula and suggest changes to meet the learners' needs ($\bar{X}=4.37$), encourage teachers to use appropriate methods of teaching ($\bar{X}=4.57$), conduct meetings with teachers to review progress, instructional concerns and exchange of ideas and materials ($\bar{X}=4.52$), and communicate with administrators about instructional concerns ($\bar{X}=4.39$).

The school heads perceive their school leadership in terms of curriculum as highly evident ($\bar{X}=4.92$). This level of school leadership is also manifested in all the indicators. Based on the results, the school heads perceive that they assist teachers in lesson planning, developing/selecting instructional ($\bar{X}=4.90$), help teachers to evaluate curricula and suggest changes to meet the learners' needs ($\bar{X}=4.80$), encourage teachers to use appropriate methods of teaching ($\bar{X}=4.90$), and communicate with administrators about instructional concerns ($\bar{X}=5.00$).

The school heads perceive the level of their school leadership in terms of curriculum as highly evident ($\bar{X}=4.96$) based on the overall mean rating. Their perception indicate that they, as school heads, participate in networks focused and has sufficient autonomy to lead the practices most likely to improve student learning ($\bar{X}=4.90$), encourage the distribution of leadership tasks across the school and support in building collaborative cultures among teachers ($\bar{X}=4.90$), demonstrate capacities to carry out teacher monitoring and evaluation and display knowledge and skills to use data effectively to improve practice ($\bar{X}=5.00$), and ensure that the composition of school personnel is consistent with their objectives and responsibilities ($\bar{X}=5.00$).

Curriculum is a standards-based sequence of planned experiences where students practice and achieve proficiency in content and applied learning skills. Curriculum is the central guide for all educators as to what is essential for teaching and learning, so that every student has access to rigorous academic experiences [15].

Management Competency of School Heads: Basis for Effective and Improved School Leadership

Table 19. Perceived Level of School Heads in School Leadership in terms of Curriculum

Indicators	Teacher		VI	School Head		VI
	Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
1. assist teachers in lesson planning, developing/selecting instructional materials, in evaluating student performance, and advise them about new developments in teaching	4.24	0.71	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
2. help teachers to evaluate curricula and suggest changes to meet the learners' needs	4.37	0.69	Evident	4.80	0.42	Highly Evident
3. encourage teachers to use appropriate methods of teaching	4.57	0.59	Highly Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
4. conduct meetings with teachers to review progress, instructional concerns and exchange of ideas and materials	4.52	0.63	Highly Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
5. communicate with administrators about instructional concerns	4.39	0.63	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
Overall Mean	4.42	0.44	Evident	4.92	0.14	Highly Evident

Academic Performance

It can be deduced from table 20 that the teachers perceive the level of the school heads' school leadership is evident ($\bar{X}=4.36$) based on the overall mean rating. According to them, the school heads participate in networks focused and has sufficient autonomy to lead the practices most likely to improve student learning ($\bar{X}=4.36$), encourage the distribution of leadership tasks across the school and support in building collaborative cultures among teachers ($\bar{X}=4.32$), demonstrate capacities to carry out teacher monitoring and evaluation and display knowledge and skills to use data effectively to improve practice ($\bar{X}=4.39$), share resources, offers necessary competencies for effective collaboration, and ensure that resource allocations are consistent with pedagogical priorities ($\bar{X}=4.36$), and ensure that the composition of school personnel is consistent with their objectives and responsibilities ($\bar{X}=4.39$).

It was pointed out that the school head's leadership and learners' academic achievements indicates that school leaders that are highly effective can intensely influence the overall academic achievement of the learners [16].

Table 20. Perceived Level of School Heads in School Leadership in terms of Academic performance

Indicators	Teacher		VI	School Head		VI
	Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
1. participate in networks focused and has sufficient autonomy to lead the practices most likely to improve student learning	4.36	0.67	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
2. encourage the distribution of leadership tasks across the school and support in building collaborative cultures among teachers	4.32	0.63	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
3. demonstrate capacities to carry out teacher monitoring and evaluation and display knowledge and skills to use data effectively to improve practice	4.39	0.65	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
4. share resources, offers necessary competencies for effective collaboration, and ensure that resource allocations are consistent with pedagogical priorities	4.36	0.67	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
5. ensure that the composition of school personnel is consistent with their objectives and responsibilities	4.39	0.65	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
Overall Mean	4.36	0.45	Evident	4.96	0.08	Highly Evident

Funding

Table 21 shows that from the teachers' perspective, the level of school leadership of the school heads in terms of funding is evident ($\bar{X}=4.33$). The same level is manifested in all the indicators. The teachers perceive that their school heads join with the management staff, heads of departments and units, prepare budgets and keep accurate financial information about the school ($\bar{X}=4.34$), prioritize financial allocation according to needs, plan the sources for funds for school improvement and ensure that budgets reflect agreed goals and objectives ($\bar{X}=4.30$), delegate the mechanism of financial matters to capable staff ($\bar{X}=4.25$), keep close check on financial matters delegated to staff and give true and fair view of the financial position of the school ($\bar{X}=4.39$), and pay attention to discuss financial reports and monitor the flow of funds and works within the constraints of the school budget ($\bar{X}=4.35$).

The school heads perceive the level of their school leadership in terms of funding as highly evident ($\bar{X}=4.96$) based on the overall mean. The same level is manifested in all the indicators. The school heads perceive that they join with the management staff, heads

Management Competency of School Heads: Basis for Effective and Improved School Leadership

of departments and units, prepare budgets and keep accurate financial information about the school ($\bar{X}=5.00$), prioritize financial allocation according to needs, plan the sources for funds for school improvement and ensure that budgets reflect agreed goals and objectives ($\bar{X}=5.00$), delegate the mechanism of financial matters to capable staff ($\bar{X}=4.25$), keep close check on financial matters delegated to staff and give true and fair view of the financial position of the school ($\bar{X}=4.90$), and pay attention to discuss financial reports and monitor the flow of funds and works within the constraints of the school budget ($\bar{X}=4.96$).

Good financial management in schools is essential to the achievement of all teaching activities of any school. School heads must keep accurate financial information about the school.

Table 21. Perceived Level of School Heads in School Leadership in terms of Funding

Indicators	Teacher		VI	School Head		VI
	Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
1. join with the management staff, heads of departments and units, prepare budgets and keep accurate financial information about the school	4.34	0.68	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
2. prioritize financial allocation according to needs, plan the sources for funds for school improvement and ensure that budgets reflect agreed goals and objectives	4.30	0.67	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
3. delegate the mechanism of financial matters to capable staff	4.25	0.72	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
4. keep close check on financial matters delegated to staff and give true and fair view of the financial position of the school	4.39	0.67	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
5. pay attention to discuss financial reports and monitor the flow of funds and works within the constraints of the school budget	4.35	0.64	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
Overall Mean	4.33	0.45	Evident	4.96	0.08	Highly Evident

Motivation

It can be drawn from table 22 that the teachers' overall perception of the level of school leadership of school heads is evident ($\bar{X}=4.43$). They perceive that the school heads showcase example of good work, behavior, loyalty, and commitment for teachers to follow as a symbol of success and accomplishment in teaching profession ($\bar{X}=4.29$), inspire teachers to aim high in our teaching job and encourage them to continue academic careers like professional development ($\bar{X}=4.38$), fuel sense of duty, work commitment, special ability and talent that are really important factor to consider in teaching profession and life ($\bar{X}=4.55$), encourage teachers to hope for a bright future in teaching profession and make them feel proud to be associated ($\bar{X}=4.51$), and stimulate and encourage teachers to participate willingly and happily in doing departmental duties and to express ideas and opinions in meetings ($\bar{X}=4.43$). Motivation drives teachers to work effectively and consistently. Adams' Equity Theory includes this essential factor. According to the theory, striving to improve an employee's job satisfaction or motivation level is important. As perceived by the teachers and the school heads, school leadership in terms of motivation is evident in the school heads.

Table 22. Perceived Level of School Heads in School Leadership in terms of Motivation

Indicators	Teacher		VI	School Head		VI
	Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
1. showcase example of good work, behavior, loyalty, and commitment for teachers to follow as a symbol of success and accomplishment in teaching profession	4.29	0.73	Evident	4.90	0.32	Highly Evident
2. inspire teachers to aim high in our teaching job and encourage them to continue academic careers like professional development	4.38	0.66	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
3. fuel sense of duty, work commitment, special ability and talent that are really important factor to consider in teaching profession and life	4.55	0.61	Highly Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
4. encourage teachers to hope for a bright future in teaching profession and make them feel proud to be associated	4.51	0.64	Highly Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
5. stimulate and encourage teachers to participate willingly and happily in doing departmental duties and to express ideas and opinions in meetings	4.44	0.61	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
Overall Mean	4.43	0.43	Evident	4.98	0.06	Highly Evident

Management Competency of School Heads: Basis for Effective and Improved School Leadership

Professional Growth

It can be drawn from table 23 that the teachers' overall perception on the level of school leadership of school heads in terms of professional growth is evident ($\bar{X}=4.37$). According to the results, the teachers perceive that the school heads have direct supervisory activities for the teachers' improvement ($\bar{X}=4.39$), encourage teachers' professional growth and help them facilitate access to professional resources ($\bar{X}=4.32$), evaluate the classroom teaching performance using more than just one source for development ($\bar{X}=4.37$), provide feedback, technical and teaching assistance and offer suggestions for instructional improvement ($\bar{X}=4.39$), and conduct in-service programs to improve the performance of teachers and orientation activities ($\bar{X}=4.40$).

The school heads perceive the level of their school leadership in terms of professional growth as highly evident ($\bar{X}=5.00$) based on their overall perception. The same level is manifested in all the indicators. Based on the school heads' perception, they have direct supervisory activities for the teachers' improvement ($\bar{X}=5.00$), encourage teachers' professional growth and help them facilitate access to professional resources ($\bar{X}=5.00$), evaluate the classroom teaching performance using more than just one source for development ($\bar{X}=5.00$), provide feedback, technical and teaching assistance and offer suggestions for instructional improvement ($\bar{X}=5.00$), and conduct in-service programs to improve the performance of teachers and orientation activities ($\bar{X}=5.00$).

Professional growth is the application of new experiences and skills to positively impact your current position and career pursuits. By expanding your skills and thinking ahead, you are preparing yourself to handle more responsibilities.

Table 23. Perceived Level of School Heads in School Leadership in terms of Professional growth

Indicators	Teacher		VI	School Head		VI
	Mean	SD		Mean	SD	
1. direct supervisory activities for the teachers' improvement	4.39	0.67	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
2. encourage teachers' professional growth and help them facilitate access to professional resources	4.32	0.62	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
3. evaluate the classroom teaching performance using more than just one source for development	4.37	0.68	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
4. provide feedback, technical and teaching assistance and offer suggestions for instructional improvement	4.39	0.63	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
5. conduct in-service programs to improve the performance of teachers and orientation activities	4.40	0.65	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident
Overall Mean	4.37	0.44	Evident	5.00	0.00	Highly Evident

3. Difference between the Perceived Level of Management Competency of the Teacher-Respondents when Grouped According to Sex

Table 24 shows the results of the t-test analyses to determine the difference in the level of management competency of school heads in terms of instructional skills, personnel skills, and financial skills from the perception of male and female teacher-respondents. The results reveal that there is no significant difference in perceived level of management competency in instructional skills of school heads in terms of School's VMGO ($p=0.734$), Supervision and Evaluation ($p=0.934$), Curricular Coordination ($p=0.171$), Curricular Coordination (0.432), Student Progress (0.432), Instructional Time (0.068), Incentives for Teachers (0.111), Incentives for Learning (0.070), and Professional Development (0.167) based on the perception of the male and female teacher-respondents. This means that in these dimensions of instructional skills, the perception of the male and female respondents about the level of management competency in instructional skills is just the same. However, there is a significant difference between the perception of male and female respondents about the management competency in instructional skills in terms of visibility ($p=0.033$) and career motivation ($p=0.012$). This means that compared to female teachers, male teachers perceive that school heads have lower visibility and lower in career motivation.

In management competency in personnel skills, there is no significant difference in the level of perception between male and female teacher-respondents in terms of communication ($p=0.683$), leadership ($p=0.058$) and decision making ($p=0.234$) of the school heads. These results mean that the perception of male and female teacher-respondents about the level of management competency is just the same at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 24. Test of difference between the perceived level of management competency of the teacher-respondents when grouped according to sex.

Management Competency	Male		Female		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Instructional skills							
a. School's VMGO	4.34	0.67	4.38	0.41	-0.341	98	0.734
b. Supervision and Evaluation	4.34	0.62	4.35	0.41	-0.083	98	0.934

Management Competency of School Heads: Basis for Effective and Improved School Leadership

c. Curricular Coordination	4.17	0.50	4.34	0.40	-1.380	98	0.171
d. Student Progress	4.26	0.60	4.38	0.47	-0.789	98	0.432
e. Instructional Time	4.18	0.53	4.40	0.37	-1.847	98	0.068
f. Visibility	4.18	0.56	4.45	0.38	-2.164	98	0.033
g. Incentives for Teachers	4.28	0.56	4.47	0.38	-1.607	98	0.111
h. Incentives for Learning	4.25	0.58	4.47	0.37	-1.832	98	0.070
i. Career Motivation	4.17	0.56	4.49	0.40	-2.546	98	0.012
j. Professional Development	4.28	0.60	4.46	0.41	-1.393	98	0.167
Personnel skills							
a. Communication	4.29	0.62	4.34	0.40	-0.410	98	0.683
b. Leadership	4.23	0.59	4.46	0.37	-1.920	98	0.058
c. Decision Making	4.22	0.65	4.38	0.43	-1.198	98	0.234
Financial skills							
a. Budget or Financial Plan	4.26	0.68	4.34	0.44	-0.554	98	0.581
b. Audit or Financial Control	4.15	0.63	4.44	0.43	-2.098	98	0.038
c. Financial Report	4.20	0.66	4.37	0.43	-1.249	98	0.215

4. Difference between the Perceived Level of Management Competency of the School Heads when Grouped According to Sex

Table 25 shows the results of the t-test analyses to determine the difference in the level of management competency of school heads in terms of instructional skills, personnel skills, and financial skills from the perception of male and female school heads.

The results reveal that there is no significant difference in the perceived level of perception between the male and female school heads on their competency management in instructional skills in terms of School's VMGO ($p=0.807$), Supervision and Evaluation ($p=0.610$), Curricular Coordination ($p=0.447$), Student Progress (0.312), Visibility (0.477), Incentives for Teachers (0.779), Incentives for Learning (0.281), Career Motivation (0.447) and Professional Development (1.000). However, there is a significant difference in the perceived level of management competency in instructional skills in terms of Instructional Time ($p=0.016$). This means that the female school heads perceive themselves to be lower in the level of instructional skills in terms of instructional time.

Table 25. Test of difference between the perceived level of management competency of the school heads when grouped according to sex

Management Competency	Male		Female		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Instructional skills							
a. School's VMGO	4.95	0.10	4.93	0.10	0.253	8	0.807
b. Supervision and Evaluation	4.95	0.10	4.90	0.17	0.531	8	0.610
c. Curricular Coordination	4.80	0.28	4.90	0.11	-0.800	8	0.447
d. Student Progress	4.90	0.12	4.97	0.08	-1.079	8	0.312
e. Instructional Time	5.00	0.00	4.77	0.15	3.037	8	0.016
f. Visibility	4.90	0.20	4.97	0.08	-0.746	8	0.477
g. Incentives for Teachers	4.90	0.20	4.93	0.16	-0.290	8	0.779
h. Incentives for Learning	4.75	0.38	4.93	0.10	-1.155	8	0.281
i. Career Motivation	5.00	0.00	4.97	0.08	0.800	8	0.447
j. Professional Development	4.80	0.16	4.80	0.25	0.000	8	1.000
Personnel skills							
a. Communication	4.95	0.10	4.93	0.16	0.181	8	0.861
b. Leadership	4.95	0.10	4.90	0.17	0.531	8	0.610
c. Decision Making	5.00	0.00	4.93	0.16	0.800	8	0.447
Financial skills							
a. Budget or Financial Plan	4.70	0.20	4.87	0.21	-1.265	8	0.242
b. Audit or Financial Control	4.80	0.28	4.83	0.23	-0.204	8	0.844
c. Financial Report	5.00	0.00	4.87	0.24	1.079	8	0.312

4. Relationship between the Teacher-Respondents' Perceived Management Competency and the School Leadership of School Heads in Lucena West District

In conducting the study, it was hypothesized that "There is no significant relationship between the management competencies and school leadership of the school heads of Lucena West District".

It can be deduced from table 26 that there is a positive and significant relationship between the independent variable, perceived management competency and the dependent variable, school leadership in all the dimensions based on the perception of the teacher-

Management Competency of School Heads: Basis for Effective and Improved School Leadership

respondents. Perceived management competency in Instructional Skills, Personnel Skills and Financial Skills are positively and significantly associated with the dimensions of school leadership skills of the school heads, namely Infrastructure, Curriculum, Academic Performance, Funding, Motivation and Professional Growth.

Instructional Skills and School Leadership

According to the results, there is a strong positive and significant correlation between school's VMGO and infrastructure ($r=0.817$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between school's VMGO and curriculum ($r=0.613$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between school's VMGO and academic performance ($r=0.949$). There is a moderately positive and significant relationship between school's VMGO and funding ($r=0.785$). There is a moderately positive and significant relationship between school's VMGO and motivation ($r=0.575$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between school's VMGO and professional growth ($r=0.913$).

There is a strong positive and significant relationship between supervision and evaluation, and infrastructure ($r=0.930$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between supervision and evaluation and curriculum ($r=0.590$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between supervision and motivation, and academic performance ($r=0.840$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between supervision and evaluation, and funding ($r=0.890$). There is a moderate positive relationship between supervision and evaluation, and motivation ($r=0.557$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between supervision and evaluation, and professional growth ($r=0.836$).

There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between curricular coordination and infrastructure ($r=0.668$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between curricular coordination and curriculum ($r=0.598$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between curricular coordination and academic performance ($r=0.794$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between curricular coordination and funding ($r=0.640$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between curricular coordination and motivation ($r=0.572$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between curricular coordination and professional growth ($r=0.790$).

There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between student progress and infrastructure ($r=0.685$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between student progress and curriculum ($r=0.619$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between student progress and academic performance ($r=0.668$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between student progress and funding ($r=0.643$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between student progress and motivation ($r=0.576$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between student progress and professional growth ($r=0.658$).

There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between instructional time and infrastructure ($r=0.617$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between instructional time and curriculum ($r=0.654$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between instructional time and academic performance ($r=0.648$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between instructional time and funding ($r=0.577$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between instructional time and motivation ($r=0.610$, $p<0.05$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between instructional time and professional growth ($r=0.631$).

There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between visibility and infrastructure ($r=0.691$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between visibility and curriculum ($r=0.779$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between visibility and academic performance ($r=0.752$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between visibility and funding ($r=0.665$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between visibility and motivation ($r=0.750$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between visibility and professional growth ($r=0.719$).

There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between incentive for teachers and infrastructure ($r=0.617$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between incentive for teachers and curriculum ($r=0.962$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between incentive for teachers and academic performance ($r=0.647$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between incentive for teachers and funding ($r=0.561$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between incentive for teachers and motivation ($r=0.903$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between incentive for teachers and professional growth ($r=0.618$).

There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between incentive for learning and infrastructure ($r=0.653$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between incentive for learning and curriculum ($r=0.840$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between incentive for learning and academic performance ($r=0.672$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between academic performance ($r=0.860$). There is a strong positive management competency and the dependent variable, school leadership in all the dimensions based on the perception of the teacher-respondents. Perceived management competency in Instructional Skills, Personnel Skills and Financial Skills are positively and significantly associated with the dimensions of school leadership skills of the school heads, namely Infrastructure, Curriculum, Academic Performance, Funding, Motivation and Professional Growth.

Management Competency of School Heads: Basis for Effective and Improved School Leadership

Instructional Skills and School Leadership

According to the results, there is a strong positive and significant correlation between school's VMGO and infrastructure ($r=0.817$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between school's VMGO and curriculum ($r=0.613$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between school's VMGO and academic performance ($r=0.949$). There is a moderately positive and significant relationship between school's VMGO and funding ($r=0.785$). There is a moderately positive and significant relationship between school's VMGO and motivation ($r=0.575$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between school's VMGO and professional growth ($r=0.913$).

There is a strong positive and significant relationship between supervision and evaluation, and infrastructure ($r=0.930$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between supervision and evaluation and curriculum ($r=0.590$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between supervision and motivation, and academic performance ($r=0.840$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between supervision and evaluation, and funding ($r=0.890$). There is a moderate positive relationship between supervision and evaluation, and motivation ($r=0.557$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between supervision and evaluation, and professional growth ($r=0.836$).

There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between curricular coordination and infrastructure ($r=0.668$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between curricular coordination and curriculum ($r=0.598$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between curricular coordination and academic performance ($r=0.794$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between curricular coordination and funding ($r=0.640$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between curricular coordination and motivation ($r=0.572$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between curricular coordination and professional growth ($r=0.790$).

There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between student progress and infrastructure ($r=0.685$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between student progress and curriculum ($r=0.619$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between student progress and academic performance ($r=0.668$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between student progress and funding ($r=0.643$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between student progress and motivation ($r=0.576$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between student progress and professional growth ($r=0.658$).

There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between instructional time and infrastructure ($r=0.617$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between instructional time and curriculum ($r=0.654$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between instructional time and academic performance ($r=0.648$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between instructional time and funding ($r=0.577$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between instructional time and motivation ($r=0.610$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between instructional time and professional growth ($r=0.631$).

There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between visibility and infrastructure ($r=0.691$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between visibility and curriculum ($r=0.779$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between visibility and academic performance ($r=0.752$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between visibility and funding ($r=0.665$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between visibility and motivation ($r=0.750$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between visibility and professional growth ($r=0.719$).

There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between incentive for teachers and infrastructure ($r=0.617$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between incentive for teachers and curriculum ($r=0.962$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between incentive for teachers and academic performance ($r=0.647$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between incentive for teachers and funding ($r=0.561$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between incentive for teachers and motivation ($r=0.903$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between incentive for teachers and professional growth ($r=0.618$).

There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between incentive for learning and infrastructure ($r=0.653$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between incentive for learning and curriculum ($r=0.840$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between incentive for learning and academic performance ($r=0.672$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between incentive for learning and funding ($r=0.606$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between incentive for learning and motivation ($r=0.791$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between incentive for learning and professional growth ($r=0.647$).

There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between career motivation and infrastructure ($r=0.634$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between career motivation and curriculum ($r=0.698$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between career motivation and academic performance ($r=0.606$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between career motivation and funding ($r=0.589$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between career motivation and motivation ($r=0.656$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between career motivation and professional growth ($r=0.592$).

Management Competency of School Heads: Basis for Effective and Improved School Leadership

There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between professional development and infrastructure ($r=0.580$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between professional development and curriculum ($r=0.857$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between professional development and academic performance ($r=0.586$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between professional development and funding ($r=0.531$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between professional development and motivation ($r=0.796$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between professional development and professional growth ($r=0.553$).

Personnel Skills and School Leadership

There is a strong positive and significant relationship between communication and infrastructure ($r=0.950$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between communication and curriculum ($r=0.593$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between communication and academic performance ($r=0.860$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between communication and funding ($r=0.923$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between communication and motivation ($r=0.555$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between communication and professional growth ($r=0.839$).

There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between leadership and infrastructure ($r=0.627$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between leadership and curriculum ($r=0.968$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between leadership and academic performance ($r=0.667$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between leadership and funding ($r=0.569$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between leadership and motivation ($r=0.900$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between leadership and professional growth ($r=0.617$).

There is a strong positive and significant relationship between decision-making and infrastructure ($r=0.851$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between decision-making and curriculum ($r=0.671$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between decision-making and academic performance ($r=0.949$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between decision-making and funding ($r=0.807$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between decision-making and motivation ($r=0.631$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between decision-making and professional growth ($r=0.934$).

Financial Skills and School Leadership

There is a strong positive and significant relationship between Budget Plan and infrastructure ($r=0.963$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between Budget Plan and curriculum ($r=0.645$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between Budget Plan and academic performance ($r=0.874$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between Budget Plan and funding ($r=0.934$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between Budget Plan and motivation ($r=0.591$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between Budget Plan and professional growth ($r=0.853$).

There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between Audit/Financial Control and infrastructure ($r=0.663$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between Audit/Financial Control and curriculum ($r=0.978$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between Audit/Financial Control and academic performance ($r=0.682$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between Audit/Financial Control and funding ($r=0.654$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between Audit/Financial Control and motivation ($r=0.941$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between Audit/Financial Control and professional growth ($r=0.660$).

There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between Financial Report and infrastructure ($r=0.883$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between Financial Report and curriculum ($r=0.709$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between Financial Report and academic performance ($r=0.973$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between Financial Report and funding ($r=0.841$). There is a strong positive and significant relationship between Financial Report and motivation ($r=0.659$). There is a moderate positive and significant relationship between Financial Report and professional growth ($r=0.962$).

The results of the Pearson's r correlation analyses show that management competency and school leadership of school heads are significantly correlated or associated with one another. This means that an increase in the level of management competency will increase the school leadership ability of the school heads.

Table 27. Test of relationship between the school-Heads'-respondents' perceived management competency and the school leadership of school heads in Lucena West District

Management Competency	School Leadership					
	Infrastructure	Curriculum	Academic Performance	Funding	Motivation	Professional Growth
Instructional skills						
a. School's VMGO	.817**	.613**	.949**	.785**	.575**	.913**
b. Supervision and Evaluation	.930**	.590**	.840**	.891**	.557**	.836**
c. Curricular Coordination	.668**	.598**	.794**	.640**	.572**	.790**

Management Competency of School Heads: Basis for Effective and Improved School Leadership

d. Student Progress	.685**	.619**	.668**	.643**	.576**	.658**
e. Instructional Time	.617**	.654**	.648**	.577**	.610**	.631**
f. Visibility	.691**	.779**	.752**	.665**	.750**	.719**
g. Incentives for Teachers	.617**	.962**	.647**	.561**	.903**	.618**
h. Incentives for Learning	.653**	.840**	.672**	.606**	.791**	.647**
i. Career Motivation	.634**	.698**	.606**	.589**	.656**	.592**
j. Professional Development	.580**	.857**	.586**	.531**	.796**	.553**
Personnel skills						
a. Communication	.950**	.593**	.860**	.923**	.555**	.839**
b. Leadership	.627**	.968**	.667**	.569**	.900**	.617**
c. Decision Making	.851**	.671**	.949**	.807**	.631**	.934**
Financial skills						
a. Budget or Financial Plan	.963**	.645**	.874**	.934**	.591**	.853**
b. Audit or Financial Control	.663**	.978**	.682**	.654**	.941**	.660**
c. Financial Report	.883**	.709**	.973**	.841**	.659**	.962**

6. Implications for Promoting an Effective and Improved Management Competency and School Leadership

Management Competency

The management competencies considered in the study can be used as guide that school heads and teachers can follow as partners to manage the schools in terms of instructional skills, personnel skills, and financial skills.

All school heads must be able to use all their capabilities to ensure that the management competencies are maintained at high levels to deliver the programs and activities of the school effectively.

School Leadership

Leadership is an essential ability that enables an individual to guide, unite or lead subordinates to accomplish a common goal or purpose. Just like in any organization, leadership is critical in leading stakeholders in a school. School leadership is positively related to management competency. Therefore, school heads should also maintain a high degree of school leadership to maintain or improve essential aspects of the school, such as the infrastructure, curriculum, academic performance, funding, motivation, and professional growth.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In the light of the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

The school heads' management competencies are evident in terms of instructional skills, personnel skills, and financial skills as perceived by the schoolteachers. The school heads' management competencies are highly evident in terms of instructional skills, personnel skills, and financial skills as perceived by the school heads.

The school leadership of the school heads is evident in terms of infrastructure, curriculum, academic performance, funding, motivation, and professional growth as perceived by the schoolteachers. The school leadership of the school heads is highly evident in terms of infrastructure, curriculum, academic performance, funding, motivation, and professional growth as perceived by the school heads.

There is no significant difference in the perceived level of management competency between male and female teacher-respondents in personnel skills, except in instructional skills in terms of visibility and career motivation. This means that compared to female teachers, male teachers perceive that school heads have lower visibility and lower in career motivation. There is also a significant difference between the perception of male and female respondents about the management competency in financial skills in terms of audit or financial control, which means that male teachers perceive school heads to have lower financial skills in terms of audit or financial control. There is no significant difference in the perceived level of management competency between male and female school heads, except in instructional skills in terms of instructional time as perceived by the school heads, which means that the female school heads perceive themselves to be lower in the level of instructional skills in terms of instructional time compared to their male counterparts.

There is a positive and significant relationship between the independent variable, perceived management competency and the dependent variable, school leadership in all the dimensions based on the perception of the teacher-respondents. However, as perceived by the school heads, there are only several positive and significant relationships that were determined. These are between school's VMGO and infrastructure, school's VMGO and academic performance, supervision and evaluation and curriculum, curricular coordination and curriculum, curricular coordination and funding, student progress and infrastructure, instructional time and academic performance, visibility and curriculum ($r=0.895$), visibility and funding, incentive for teachers and infrastructure, career motivation and funding, professional development and funding, professional development and funding ($r=-0.500$), communication and academic performance, and Budget Plan and curriculum.

Management Competency of School Heads: Basis for Effective and Improved School Leadership

In terms of management competency and school leadership, the school heads must use all the factors or indicators considered in the study as guide in school management and school leadership because these factors are evident as perceived by the teacher-respondents. Hence, the school heads are doing their functions as managers and leaders of their schools.

REFERENCES

- 1) Lipham, J. (2016). *The principalship: Foundations and functions* (3rd ed.). New York: Harper and Row.
- 2) Egwu, S.O. (2016). Management strategies for conflict resolution in secondary schools in Ebonyi state, Nigeria. *UNIZIK Journal of Educational Management and Policy*, 1(1), 88-94
- 3) Ikegbusi, N.G. & Iheanacho, R.C. (2016). Factors militating against effective administration of secondary schools in Anambra state. *World Journal of Educational Research*, 3(1), 213-226
- 4) Carol, A.F. & Edward, P.S. (2004). *Clinical supervision: A competency-based approach*. USA: Amazon Kindle
- 5) Heller, C.R. (2012). *School manager's handbook*. London: Dorling Kindersley Limited
- 6) McNamara, C. (2016). *Building basic skills in management and leadership*. Free Management Library: Connect Soft Ltd
- 7) Adaegebe, S.U. (2016). *Curriculum innovation and the secondary school principals*. Ife: Institute of Education University Press
- 8) Creswell, J.W. & Creswell, J.D. (2018). *Research Design Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches Fifth Edition*. SAGE Publication, Inc
- 9) Bhandari, P. (2022). Ethical Considerations in Research Types and Examples. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/research-ethics/>
- 10) Orsmond, P. and S. Merry. (2021). Feedback Alignment, Effective and Ineffective Links Between Tutors' and Students' Understanding of Coursework Feedback, Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education, Vol. 36/2, Pp. 125-136, [Http://Dx.Doi.Org/10.1080/02602930903201651](http://Dx.Doi.Org/10.1080/02602930903201651)
- 11) Stremmel, A.J. (2019). Pedagogical Leadership as Ethical Collaborative Behaviour in S. Chessman & R. Walker (Eds.), *Pedagogies for Leading Practice*, Pp. 78–90, Routledge, Oxon
- 12) Absolum, M., Michael, H., & Julio, Y. (2021). *Directions for Assessment in New Zealand: Developing Students' Assessment Capabilities*, Ministry of Education, Wellington
- 13) Nusche, 2021 Nusche, D. Marco, J. K., & Julius, Y. (2021). *OECD Reviews of Evaluation and Assessment in Education: Norway 2011, OECD Reviews of Evaluation and Assessment in Education*, OECD Publishing, Paris
- 14) UNESCO (2023). *Instructional time and classroom management* <https://learningportal.iiep.unesco.org/en/issue-briefs/improve-learning/instructional-time-and-classroom-management>
- 15) Department of Education State of Rhode Island (2023). *Curriculum Definition*. <https://ride.ri.gov/instruction-assessment/curriculum/curriculum-definition>
- 16) Marzano, R.J., Waters, T, & McNulty, B.A. (2015). *School leadership that works*. Alexandria, VA: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development (ASCD).